

Synthesis and Hypoglycemic Activity of Some New N-p-(Hydrazonocarbonyl)Phenyl-4-Substituted Benzene Sulphonamides

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A series of N-p-(hydrazonocarbonyl)phenyl 4-substituted benzene sulphonamides were synthesised by refluxing 4-(p-substituted benzene sulphonamido) benzoic acid hydrazides with various aldehyde or ketone in absolute ethanol in presence of glacial acetic acid. Fifteen of these compounds when screened on the albino rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg reduced the blood sugar level to a significant extent.

RECENTLY, a few sulphonamide derivatives have been reported to possess antitubercular^{1,2} and hypoglycemic³ activities. Some long chain sulphonamides⁴ have also been known to decrease the blood glucose level in animals. Moreover, a few derivatives of semicarbazone⁵ having >C=N-linkage have been found to be mildly active in producing hypoglycemia. This led us to synthesise the title sulphonamides containing >C=N-linkage in order to study their hypoglycemic efficacy.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrometer 157 in KBr pellets. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested by tlc.

Ethyl-4-(p-substituted benzene sulphonamido) benzoates (I): The compounds were synthesised according to the method of El-Kerdawcy *et al.*¹. Equimolar quantities of ethyl p-amino benzoate and p-substituted phenylsulphonyl chloride were fused on a water bath for 30 min. A solid separated on cooling the reaction mixture, which crystallized from ethanol. The four benzoates thus prepared are (1) R=H, m.p. 181° (Found: N, 5.22. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₆SNO₄; N, 4.90%); (2) R=CH₃, m.p. 175-77° (Found: N, 4.35. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈SNO₄; N, 4.68%); (3) R=OCH₃, m.p. 170° (Found: N, 4.92. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₈SNO₅; N, 4.68%) and (4) R=CH₃CONH, m.p. 183° (Found: N, 7.38. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₉SN₂O₅; N, 7.74%).

4-(p-Substituted benzene sulphonamido) benzoic acid hydrazides (II): A mixture of ethyl 4-(p-substituted benzene sulphonamido) benzoate (I) (0.05 mole), hydrazine hydrate (98%) (0.25 mole) and absolute ethanol (75 ml) was refluxed on a steam

bath for 8 hr. A solid mass was obtained on cooling. It was filtered and crystallised from benzene. The hydrazides thus obtained are (1) R=H, m.p. 210° (Found: N, 14.08. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₂SO₄; N, 14.38%); (2) R=CH₃, m.p. 188° (Found: N, 13.98. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₂SO₄; N, 13.72%); (3) R=CH₃, m.p. 160° (Found: N, 12.63. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₂SO₄; N, 13.04%) and (4) R=CH₃CONH, m.p. 200° (Found: N, 16.32. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇N₂SO₄; N, 16.04%).

N-p-(Hydrazonocarbonyl) phenyl-4-substituted benzene sulphonamides: Hydrazide (II) (0.005 mole), an appropriate aldehyde or ketone (0.005 mole), absolute ethanol (25 ml) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid were refluxed on a water bath. Subsequent cooling gave a solid which was washed with dil. ethanol and crystallised from ethanol.

The pertinent data of the compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Fifteen of the synthesised compounds (Table 1) were screened for their hypoglycemic activity. Albino rats weighing approximately 200 g each were kept fasting for 18 hr. Blood samples were drawn from the tail veins of the rats and their glucose content estimated by the method of Somogyi⁶. The compounds to be tested after being emulsified with 5% gum tragacanth were administered orally at a single dose of 250 mg/kg body weight. The blood samples were again drawn from the tail vein at intervals of 1, 2 and 4 hr and their glucose content estimated as above. The percentage change in glucose level was calculated.

From the results recorded in Table 1, it is difficult to arrive at a definite trend in SAR of the

TABLE 1—N-p-(HYDRAZONO CARBONYL) PHENYL-4-SUBSTITUTED BENZENE SULPHONAMIDES*

Sl. No.	R	R ¹	R ²	m.p. °C	Yield %	Average maximum reduction of blood sugar at a dose of 250 mg/kg body weight (%)
1.	H	H	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	171	80	16
2.	H	H	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -6-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	180	86	14
3.	H	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	167	75	—
4.	CH ₃ CONH	H	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	230	60	18
5.	CH ₃ CONH	H	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	230	69	—
6.	CH ₃ CONH	H	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -6-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	222	76	12
7.	CH ₃ CONH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	210	68	—
8.	OCH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₅	165	62	—
9.	OCH ₃	H	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	140d	60	19
10.	OCH ₃	H	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	145	70	21
11.	OCH ₃	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	141	73	—
12.	OCH ₃	H	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	140	75	18
13.	OCH ₃	H	4-(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	144	68	—
14. ^a	OCH ₃	H	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	140	62	16
15.	OCH ₃	H	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ -6-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	150	70	—
16.	OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	149	70	—
17.	CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₅	216	82	14
18.	CH ₃	H	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	200	80	9
19.	CH ₃	H	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	203	79	14
20.	CH ₃	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	204	85	13
21.	CH ₃	H	4-(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	201	74	—
22. ^b	CH ₃	H	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	207	81	11
23.	CH ₃	H	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ -6-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₃	200	89	9
24.	CH ₃	H	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	151	80	—
25.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	204	70	20

* Showed IR spectral bands at 1150–1140 cm⁻¹ (-HNO₂S), 1670–1660 cm⁻¹ (CONH-), 1630–1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) and 3320–3140 cm⁻¹ (-NH str.)

Satisfactory analysis for C, H and N were obtained.

a. Found : S, 7.42, Calcd. S, 7.22%

b. Found : S, 7.31, Calcd. S, 7.51%

compounds. Nevertheless, an increasing trend in the reduction of blood sugar was found in the following order of the substituents (R) H < CH₃ < NHAc < OCH₃. The above trend also shows that substitution at the p-position in phenyl ring increases the hypoglycemic efficacy. The maximum reduction of 21% in blood glucose was shown by compound no. 10.

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